

A DISTINCTIVE ORIGINALITY IN THE SHORT STORIES OF OLMAS UMARBЕКOV

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the character of Abdullah in the novel "It's Hard to Be a Man" by Olmas Umarbekov, the character of Zuhra, one of the main characters of the novel "Fatima and Zuhra", in "Autumn Air" and Solihabibi in "Yer Yonganda" are in the plot of the story. The analysis of the female image of the unique character and emotional experiences of a person is given.

Key words: Olmas Umarbekov, plot, image, character, type, evolution, female image, human psychology, artistic tool, character, detective novel, artistic idea, interpretation of images.

АННОТАЦИЯ.

В данной статье рассмотрен персонаж Абдуллы в романе Олмаса Умарбекова «Трудно быть мужчиной», персонаж Зухры, одного из главных героев романа «Фатима и Зухра», в «Осенний воздух» и Солихабиби в «Йер Йонганда» находятся в сюжете повести. Дан анализ женского образа неповторимого характера и душевных переживаний человека.

Ключевые слова: Олмас Умарбеков, сюжет, образ, персонаж, тип, эволюция, женский образ, психология человека, художественный инструмент, персонаж, детективный роман, художественная идея, интерпретация образов.

O'lmas Umarbekov, a mature writer and creative figure of the Uzbek people, is regarded as one of the authors whose stories and novels have deeply penetrated the hearts of readers. Although he began his career as a journalist, by the 1960s he had already gained recognition among his contemporaries and mentors through his significant contributions to Uzbek prose, particularly in the genre of short stories.

The fact that the writer developed his own unique style in Uzbek short story writing became especially evident in the literary processes of the 1960s. In dozens of stories such as "Yulduzlar", "Oltin yaproqlar", "Charos", "Yo'lda", "Ko'prik", and "Qiyomat qarz", the author strives to reveal the noble qualities of human beings and the dramatic experiences of the human soul. This feature rises to the level of a leading ideological and aesthetic principle in his works. In general, through the embodiment of important moral and ethical qualities in people and the exploration of diverse character types, the writer succeeds in illuminating broader issues such as human destiny, conscience, responsibility toward the future and society, and faith.

Characters such as Sarvi xola in "Kuz havosi", Solihabibi in "Yer yonganda", Zuhra in "Fatima and Zuhra", and Abdullah in "It Is Difficult to Be a Man" vividly portray the diversity of human emotions and inner experiences. These characters allow readers to reflect deeply and to better understand the unique traits of the protagonists in both stories and novels. In Umarbekov's works, social realities are reflected through the distinct characteristics of the characters.

In the story “Yer yonganda”, social events are revealed through the character of Solihabibi. Her son is imprisoned for allegedly taking a bribe, yet she refuses to believe the accusation and considers it slander.

At the end of the story, Solihabibi finds gold coins hidden in a container. Unable to bear the truth, she sets herself on fire and commits suicide. In her character, honor and dignity prevail; not her son, but she herself becomes the victim of society. The narrative demonstrates the dominance of psychological conditions in human life and shows how easily an individual may choose an irreversible path under emotional pressure. This transformation reveals the strong influence of consciousness on the character and provides another dimension of interpretation.

Through the character of Zumrad in the story “Nomus”, we observe the multifaceted nature of literary images. Literary critic Umarali Normatov notes that the story describes a young man named Komil who falls in love with a girl named Zumrad. However, due to his mother’s will, he marries another woman. Later, he meets Zumrad again, but is unjustly accused and imprisoned. Eventually, Zumrad, despite her internal struggles and sense of honor, tells the truth in court and saves him from punishment. Through this character, the writer reveals the depth of human emotions, portraying Zumrad as sincere, loyal, and self-sacrificing.

In the novel “It Is Difficult to Be a Man”, Abdullah is initially depicted as a sincere, hardworking, and conscientious young man. However, psychological trauma experienced during his school years leads him to become ambitious and obsessed with status. The change in people’s attitudes toward him after his father loses his position, as well as the hypocrisy of his father’s friend, deeply affects him. Abdullah comes to believe that only the most powerful individuals are respected in society.

He faces a crucial moral dilemma: whether to remain loyal to Gulchehra and marry her, thereby saving her from a difficult situation, or to marry Sayyora and secure a prosperous future. Despite his academic excellence and achievements, Abdullah fails this fundamental test of humanity. Although everyone is born human, not everyone proves worthy of this title. His actions toward Gulchehra reveal a lack of moral integrity.

Ambition is portrayed as a negative trait, as it often leads individuals to hypocrisy and moral degradation. Abdullah’s father, G’ofur aka, serves as a contrasting character—an honest and humble man who never pursued power or wealth but earned respect through his humanity.

The novel “Fatima and Zuhra” was warmly received by readers and literary critics due to its actuality and strong artistic foundation. The work belongs to the detective genre, and its system of characters includes both simple and complex figures, each playing a significant role in the narrative.

Zuhra, a strong female character, is driven by the desire to avenge the tragic deaths of her twin sister Fatima, her father, and her brother. Initially a naive and innocent 17-year-old girl, she undergoes profound transformation due to life’s hardships. She becomes strong-willed, determined, and fearless.

For example, in one scene she declares:

“I am Fatima—the one you tortured and killed. I have come for revenge.”

In another dialogue with a police officer, Zuhra speaks openly and confidently, demonstrating her intelligence and courage. Despite her youth, she approaches situations with deep reasoning and is unafraid to express her opinions, even in front of men.

The final stories of O'lmas Umarbekov — which may also be regarded as the writer's testament encourage readers toward purity and righteous living, while warning against the consequences of immorality. Even in his final moments, O'lmas Umarbekov did not betray the pen. Until his heart ceased to beat, he continued to wish goodness for people. He lived loving humanity until his very last breath.

From this perspective, O'lmas Umarbekov faithfully fulfilled his duty to the Motherland and the people who educated, nurtured, and sustained him. In other words, through his sincere lines, he erected a monument to himself.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the stories of O'lmas Umarbekov present diverse types and characters of female images. The writer integrates life's realities into the psychological world of female characters, creating artistic, social, and political layers of meaning. The nature of artistic images is multifaceted, leading to the formation of typified characters.

A common feature of the analyzed works is the deep psychological portrayal of characters, which reflects the writer's unique style. It is important to emphasize that societal factors not only influence human psychology but also serve as an essential artistic tool in revealing character traits.

The novel "It Is Difficult to Be a Man" vividly reflects the realities of life, distinguished by its simplicity of language and liveliness of events. O'lmas Umarbekov holds a unique place in the development of Uzbek prose in the second half of the 20th century.

The character of Zuhra in "Fatima and Zuhra" represents a relatively innovative image for its time. While Uzbek literature includes other strong female characters, a fearless female detective figure is rare. Umarbekov's originality and mastery in character creation are clearly reflected in this character. In the spiritual renewal of human consciousness, the role of literature and the works created by our poets and writers is invaluable. This is because such works embody the national values and traditions of our people. The works of O'zbekiston People's Writer O'lmas Umarbekov serve as a vivid example of this.

The writer left behind a good and honorable legacy through his works on a wide range of themes. The relevance of our study is determined based on these issues. The protagonists of the works belonging to the pen of O'lmas Umarbekov are individuals of different eras with diverse destinies. However, the writer's heart encompasses all of them — each one is born from the writer's own soul. It would not be an exaggeration to say that these characters resemble the author himself.

Like everyone else, O'lmas Umarbekov experienced the bitter and sweet aspects of life; he witnessed betrayal, cruelty, and hypocrisy. Yet, he did not remain powerless in the face of such vices; rather, he believed in goodness and relied on truth.

Whether we read his novels such as "It Is Difficult to Be a Man" and "Fatima and Zuhra", his novellas like "My Love, My Beloved...", "Summer Rain", "Jura Village", or nearly a hundred short stories, A slogan like this would be appropriate for all the works of O'lmas Umarbekov.

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